

Precipitation variability on the massif Forest of Mahouna (North Eastern-Algeria) from 1986 to 2010

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Abstract

Water availability is a strong driver of structure and function of the ecosystems. We know that water can be very sensitive to temporal changes in precipitation. However, the analysis of precipitation variability plays an important role in the way it influences ecological and agricultural water requirements. The area chosen for this study is located in the North-East of Algeria in the province of Guelma on the massif forest of Mahouna which is a mediterranean area. This article examines annual, seasonal, monthly and daily rainfall over the region from 1986 to 2010. The temporal variation, season and daily distribution of the precipitation were analyzed using precipitation index and statistically analyses (t-test of student and Pearson correlation). The results show that spring and autumn have the same mean of the amount of precipitation; however, the spring precipitation was correlated positively and very strongly with annual precipitation. The climate of the massif forest of Mahouna is characterized by alternate wet and dry seasons from year to year.

Key words: precipitation, mediterranean area, forest of Mahouna, climate

1. Introduction

In the present context of climate change and preservation of biodiversity, the appreciation of the vulnerability of the natural ecosystems and their capacity of adaptation appears among the main preoccupations to the world level (GIEC, 2007). This assessment of the ecosystems requires the studies of climatic data and especially the rainfall variability which is a strong driver of ecosystem structure and function among all terrestrial biomes (Knapp and Smith, 2001). While mean annual precipitation is most often used to describe ecosystem water relations, it is becoming increasingly clear that the temporal dynamics of precipitation, such as seasonal distribution and the size and frequency of events can significantly modify ecosystem response to total precipitation quantity (Swemmer and al., 2007). The timing of precipitation can directly influence abiotic soil processes such as drainage, infiltration, evaporation, soil temperature, and water availability for uptake by plants (Austin and al., 2004). Therefore, a better understanding of precipitation variability on a regional scale will assist in determining water management policies. It will also help in planning sustainable agricultural practices that will contribute to ecological conservation and environmental protection.

This study will specifically focus on the daily, monthly and annual rainfall analyses in few long times of the massif forest of Mahouna in north eastern Algeria. We build a meta database of the variability of the precipitation that is a necessary first step to identify the main causes of uncertainty in agriculture future projections in the region, and a fundamental prerequisite to produce reliable assessments (Challinor et al., 2009).

The main objectives of this paper were: (i) to explore variability on both monthly and seasonal regime of precipitation; (ii) to determinate the most sensitive events such as the shortening of the season of rain or decrease in the annual number of rainy days; and (iii) to study the relationship between number of days of rainfall and the amount of rain according to the seasons and years;

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

The study was undertaken in the North East of Algeria, on the massif forest of Mahouna (from long 7°19' to long 7°27'E and from lat 36°21' to lat 36°27'N). This massif is located in the province of Guelma in the town of Bendjerrah and covers about 14000ha (Fig. 1). It is between 219 to 1411m elevation. The climate is typically Mediterranean with a mean annual temperature of 17.5°C and mean annual rainfall of around

652mm. The study area is characterized by a very important biodiversity in the plant communities from maquis of oleolentisque, ripisylve of *Tamarix* and *Ulmus campestris*, and also dense and clear forests which are dominated by mixed stands of *Quercus coccifera*, *Quercus suber* and *Quercus canariensis* (Beldjazia and al., 2012).

Fig. 1. Study area location (red shading). The map base provides the locations of the massif forest of Mahouana in image of Landsat ETM (2000) composition true color (Bandes : 3+2+1).

2.2. Data description

For this study, monthly and annual precipitations data from Algeria Meteorological Administration were gathered from Belkhier meteorological station located throughout North-East Algeria in the province of Guelma during a period from January, 1986 to December, 2010 and daily data from January, 2000 to December, 2010. The 25 years period investigated was considered long enough to a certain reliable climatic conclusions for which to reveal variability of precipitation in this site, however, 1986 was the date of the installation of meteorological state of Belkhier.

2.3. Methodology

2.3.1. Index of precipitation

In order to understand the temporal variation of the precipitation data, a numerical index was established to characterize the rainfall regime and its evolution using three different values of precipitation (daily, monthly and annual precipitation). The PI was designed to quantify the precipitation deficit for multiple timescales. Positive PI values indicate greater than median precipitation and negative values indicate less than median precipitation.

Index of precipitation (PI) is calculated with Nicholson method (Nicholson S.E., 1988) of each year and is expressed as follows:

$$I_i = (X_i - \bar{X})/S$$

with: X_i = rain height of the year i in mm; \bar{X} = rain height average in mm over the study period ; S = standard deviation of the rain height over the study period .

2.3.2. The Student's *t*-test

The *t*-test (Hald, 1952; Panofsky and Brier, 1968) assesses whether the means of two groups are not statistically different from each other (null hypothesis $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$). This test is used with Statistica to compare the mean season precipitation of the four seasons (winter, spring, summer and autumn), each season to other.

2.3.2. The time of Rainy Season and its duration

This analysis deals with daily rainfall data of the four seasons (winter, spring, summer and autumn) over 11 years period (2000-2010). The values were statistically analyzed using linear trend in Excel and the Pearson correlation coefficient by Statistica.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Variation of the seasonal rainfall regime

A detailed knowledge of the rainfall regime is an important prerequisite for agriculture planning. In this case we adopted the method of "divide the year into four quarters astronomical, so that the initial month of each quarter contains either a solstice or an equinox" (Halimi A., 1980). The winter was defined as the period of December, January and February (DJF); Spring integrates the months from March to May (MAM); the summer months from June to August (JJA) and autumn period from September to November (SON). The analysis of seasonal precipitation shows that it is different from one year to another, with a dominance of the spring rainfall in the years 1987, 1991, 1992, 1998, 2000, 2007 and 2009. While for the rest of the year the highest amount of rainfall is recorded in the winter season. For 1997 and 2010, the autumn season was the rainiest. (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The seasonal rainfall regime variation between 1986 and 2010 of the station of Belkhier (Northeast of Algeria).

These results were statistically analyzed using t-test of student to compare each season to another. The results show that the difference between the spring and autumn are not significant, that means that they have the same value of the amount of precipitation, however, the differences between all the rest of seasons are significant which indicate that winter and summer have different values of the amount of precipitation (tab.1).

Table 1. t-test of student for seasons

	Su-Au	Sp-Au	Sp-Su	Wi-Au	Wi-Su	Wi-Sp
Difference	-111.5440	36.5080	148.0520	88.5080	200.0520	52.0000
t (Observed value)	-7.9416	2.0216	9.2040	3.8397	10.8301	2.1846
t (Crical value)	2.0639	2.0639	2.0639	2.0106	2.0106	2.0106
DF	24	24	24	48	48	48
p-value (Two- tailed)	<0.0001	0.0545	<0.0001	0.0004	<0.0001	0.0338
alpha	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

Wi: Winter, Sp: Spring, Su: Summer, Au: Autumn

3.2. Variation of precipitation on a monthly time scale

In order to characterize precipitation on a regional scale, the measurements monthly data were temporally averaged throughout the period from 1986 to 2010 to illustrate dominant patterns in seasonal cycle. Monthly precipitation was highly variable. Fig. 3 shows a strong peak in January in monthly distribution, however, in July we observed a low value of the amount of precipitation.

Fig. 3. The monthly precipitation variation averaged between 1986 and 2010 throughout Northeast Algeria on the massif forest of Mahouna.

3.2. The rainfall index for the period 1986-2010

Several methodological points need to be clarified in order to claim relevant way to characterize the rainy season through this index. Clearly, a positive or negative PI calculated means that the area is experiencing a wet or dry period (Abdou A. et al., 2008).

Fig. 3. The seasonal rainfall index of the amount of rainfall during the period 1986 -2010.

The climate of the massif forest of Mahouna is characterized by alternate wet and dry seasons from year to year. The results indicate that the year 2003 had a very wet winter however, the extreme drought was observed in the year 2000.

In spring, the analysis shows 11 wet years and the rests were dry years with the extreme drought in the year 2002.

In the year 2004, summer had a high humidity however; a dry period was noticed in the year 2003.

The autumn had very important wet periods with the highest positive index in 1997.

It is generally accepted that the Mediterranean climate characterized by the irregularity of the rainfall, which can vary considerably from year to year. Rain does not fall evenly, nor does the rain arrive yearly at the same time or within the same intervals (Web, 2016).

3.3. Analysis of daily seasonal rainfall for the period 2000-2010

Changes in seasonal rainfall during the period (2000-2010), show that the winter season is experiencing a temporal distribution almost homogeneous, with a strong tendency at the beginning and a bit of weakness in the end of the season. For the spring season, we note that the rainfall amount down in a sensible manner, with an average of 2.18 mm daily. It was important at the beginning of the season. In summer, the average rainfall significantly declines with a daily average not exceeding 0.4 mm with no rainy days especially in the middle of the season in July (the driest month of the region). In autumn, average values vary between 0.1 and 2 mm with a few days of heavy rain in the end of the season (November) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Evolution seasonal daily rainfall of Belkeir station (Guelma) for 2000-2010.

These results were statistically analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient from index precipitation of number of days of rainfall and amount precipitation through the years and seasons (tab.2).

Table 2. Correlation matrix (Pearson)

variables	PI (d)y	PI (p)y	PI (d)w	PI (p)w	PI (d)sp	PI (p)sp	PI (d)su	PI (p)su	PI (d)a	PI (p)a
PI (d)y	1	0.8270	0.5407	0.0781	0.8011	0.7835	0.2656	0.4513	0.6955	0.7471
PI (p)y	0.8270	1	0.5935	0.5031	0.6467	0.8023	-0.206	0.2263	0.6539	0.5659
PI (d)w	0.5407	0.5935	1	0.6641	0.0492	0.4480	-0.3539	-0.1611	0.2019	-0.0851
PI (p)w	0.0781	0.5031	0.6641	1	-0.2652	0.1006	-0.6764	-0.3929	0.0563	-0.3158
PI (d)sp	0.8011	0.6467	0.0492	-0.2652	1	0.6876	0.4245	0.7066	0.4635	0.8663
PI (p)sp	0.7835	0.8023	0.4480	0.1006	0.6876	1	-0.1331	0.1357	0.6401	0.5102
PI (d)su	0.2656	-0.2060	-0.3539	-0.6764	0.4245	-0.1331	1	0.6989	0.0162	0.4516
PI (p)su	0.4513	0.2263	-0.1611	-0.3929	0.7066	0.1357	0.6989	1	0.0326	0.6124
PI (d)a	0.6955	0.6539	0.2019	0.0563	0.4635	0.6401	0.0162	0.0326	1	0.6955
PI (p)a	0.7471	0.5659	-0.0851	-0.3158	0.8663	0.5102	0.4516	0.6124	0.6955	1

Values in bold are different from 0 with a significance level $\alpha=0,05$

PI(d): precipitation index of number of days of rainfall

PI(P): precipitation index of amount of rainfall

y: yearly, w: winter, sp: spring, su: summer, a: autumn

The sign of the correlation coefficient determines whether the correlation is positive or negative. The magnitude of the correlation coefficient determines the strength of the correlation.

Correlation is an effect size and so we can verbally describe the strength of the correlation using the guide that Evans (1996) suggests for the absolute value of r:

- 0.00-0.19: “very weak”
- 0.20-0.39: “weak”

- 0.40-0.59: “moderate”
- 0.60-0.79: “strong”
- 0.80-1.0: “very strong”

The Pearson correlation coefficient appears a very strong positive correlation between yearly amount of precipitation and yearly number of days of precipitation, and also between the yearly precipitation and spring precipitation which confirms that when yearly precipitation (days and amount) increases (or decreases), spring precipitation will decrease (or increase). However, a strong negative correlation is produced between the amount of precipitation of winter and the number of days of precipitation in summer which means that when winter has a very important amount of precipitation, summer will have a few number of days of precipitation.

We also note that there appears a strong positive correlation between the autumn precipitation and yearly precipitation.

3. Conclusion

Precipitation is one of the most important resources of water for the forest ecosystem. These variables being useful in diagnosing climate change which affect the forests. The area chosen for this study is in the Northern East of Algeria on the massif forest of Mahouna which is located in the province of Guelma. This study has been concerned on the seasonal rainfall regime and daily distribution of the amount of precipitation during a period from 1986 to 2010. The variables were analyzed using precipitation index and statistically analyses (t-test of Student, Pearson correlation and linear trend). The results show that the massif forest of Mahouna had alternative wet and dry seasons from year to year, and a strong peak of the amount of precipitation were observed in January in monthly distribution. A daily seasonal rainfall analyzed illustrates a temporal distribution almost homogeneous, with a strong tendency at the beginning and a bit of weakness in the end of the seasons of winter and spring, however, in autumn, average values vary between 0.1 and 2 mm with a few days of heavy rain in the end of the season. Statistically analyzing showed that spring and autumn had the same mean of the amount of precipitation, while daily and amount of spring precipitation were decreasing (or increasing) with annual precipitation.

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